

Best Colleague and Role Model

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Abstract: I am sure Nina's retirement will open up a new chapter of her career, and she will continue to be an example of what a great academic researcher and mentor is about. I wish her all the best.

Keywords: Role model, control performance assessment, inspiration, dedication to scientific research.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nina has been one of my best colleagues and role models in my academic career. I knew Nina since the early 1990s when I was a graduate student at the University of Alberta. We worked in the same subject related to Control Performance Assessment in which Nina is a pioneer in applying this then-new technology to process industry achieving real industrial benefits. Since then, Nina has given me many inspirations about how to conduct research and industrial applications. She truly sets a role model of sincerity, dedication, and persistence in pursuing research and applications. She spent one of her sabbatical leaves at the University of Alberta. Even though she was already a well-established researcher, she worked day and night in our laboratory conducting actual experiments in a pilot-scale heated-tank system. She investigated all detailed phenomena of the process including the source of disturbances and quantization error. I was deeply moved by her dedication to scientific research. The best testimony of her dedication is her publications. Her publications are all solid and well-received. Her paper, Thornhill, N. F., B. Huang, and H. Zhang (2003), received Journal of Process Control Best Paper Award, in the category "methodology/theory" for the period 2002 to 2005. She gave me a lot of encouragement during my academic career including nominating me for awards. Several of her publications are also the main sources of references for my research including her pioneering work on oscillation

detection. The following are examples of our joint publications.

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Fig. 1. The photo was taken on 11 Oct 2018 at the University of Alberta, Edmonton, Canada.